

PREPARATION AND THE PROPERTIES OF SiC/MoSi₂ COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Hot press sintering and hot press reaction sintering techniques have been used to prepare SiC particle reinforced MoSi₂ composites. Microstructure of hot pressed SiCp(20vol%)/MoSi₂ composite showed uniform distribution of 1~3μm sized SiC particles in MoSi₂ matrix. *In situ* SiC/MoSi₂ composite had a 97.5% relative density. SiC particle had a size less than 1μm and a volume fraction of 15%. Composites prepared by both the routes have been found to possess higher flexural strength, indentation fracture toughness and hardness compared to monolithic MoSi₂. Compressive tests done at 1200°C and 1400°C showed that 0.2% compressive proof strength of both composites was increased obviously. Vickers hardness values of composites at 800°C have been found to be improved compared to MoSi₂.

KEYWORDS: molybdenum disilicide silicon carbide composites, hot press, reaction sintering, flexural strength, indentation fracture toughness, compressive strength, hot hardness

INTRODUCTION

Intermetallic matrix composites (IMCs) are currently being investigated for high temperature structural applications. Molybdenum-disilicide (MoSi₂) intermetallic is a promising candidate for the applications in oxidizing atmospheres. Its melting point (2030°C) is higher than Fe-Al, Ni-Al and Ti-Al intermetallic compounds and it has excellent oxidizing and thermal corrosion resistances. Its outstanding oxidation resistance is a result of the formation of a glassy silica (SiO₂), which is a very protective, adherent and coherent layer [1]. However, in most of intermetallics, the major problems include extreme brittleness and poor impact strength at a lower temperature, and an insufficient strength and creep resistance at elevated temperatures. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the room-temperature fracture toughness, elevated-temperature strength and creep resistance, if MoSi₂ is to be used as structural material. Previous studies show that an improved strengthening/toughening is possible through the incorporation of second phase reinforcements, that is, reinforcing MoSi₂ matrix with ceramic particle, whisker or continuous fiber. MoSi₂ is stable in contact with a large number of carbide, nitride, oxide and boride ceramic reinforcements, such as SiC, TiC, Si₃N₄, ZrO₂, Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃, TiB₂ and ZrB₂ at elevated temperature. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the preparation of MoSi₂ based intermetallic matrix composites [1~7]. Amongst the reinforcements used, SiC is considered to be more desired. The results of Gac *et al* [8] have shown that room-temperature flexural strength and fracture toughness of SiC

whisker/MoSi₂ composite were 310 MPa and 8.2MPam^{1/2}, respectively, and they were higher by 100% and 54%, compared to the matrix. Ghosh *et al* [3] reported that the hot hardness of SiC particle/MoSi₂ composite was higher than the monolithic MoSi₂ at temperatures below 1400°C .

The purpose of the present work is to enhance the room-temperature toughness and the high temperature strength, by incorporating SiC particle in MoSi₂ matrix. For this, hot press sintering and *in situ* reaction sintering process have been employed to fabricate SiC particle reinforced MoSi₂ composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

98.5% pure SiC (-150 mesh), 99.5% pure Mo₂C (-300 mesh), 99% pure Si(-200 mesh), 99.9% pure MoSi₂ (-120 mesh), were used in the present study. The powder mixture containing about 20 vol% of SiC and 80 vol% of MoSi₂, the mixture of Mo₂C and Si in a molar ratio of 1:5 were wet mixed in ethyl alcohol and milled for 48h, in different ball grinding cans of a planetary ball miller. The resulting powder mixtures were then cold formed in a graphite die and sintered in a vacuum furnace. After evacuating the furnace, it was filled with argon and the mixture containing the die was heated. The mixture of SiC and MoSi₂ was hot pressed at 1600°C at 24.5MPa for 45min. This yielded SiCp/MoSi₂ composite. Similar conditions were employed to prepare monolithic MoSi₂. The mixture of Mo₂C and Si was hot pressed at 1350°C for 2h and then at 1700°C for 1h under 27.5 MPa pressure. During hot pressing the following chemical reaction is expected to take place: Mo₂C + 5Si → SiC + 2MoSi₂, SiC would form *in situ* in the matrix of MoSi₂ resulting in SiC/MoSi₂ composite.

The optical and SEM observations were carried out for understanding the microstructure, reinforcing phase distribution and fractograph of all the three materials. Phase identification was done by a GEIGER-FLEX X-ray diffractometer. A Thermoflex TG-DTA was used to know the endothermic and exothermic reaction during composite fabrication using mixture of Mo₂C and Si powder.

Flexural strength was determined from 3-point bend test, using a cross head speed of 0.05 mm/min and a span length of 20 mm. 3×4×30mm size specimen were cut by electro-discharge machining. Vickers hardness indentations were used to estimate the room-temperature fracture toughness(K_{IC}). For this the average length of indentation crack was measured using an Interactive Image Analysis System(IBAS-2), and K_{IC} was calculated by the following equation [9] :

$$K_{IC} = 0.0752P(1/C)^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

where P is the load (98N and 196N were used), C is the crack half-length. Meanwhile, Vickers hardness (Hv) was also calculated. In addition 3-point bend test was also used to measure K_{IC}. For this 16mm span length specimen was used. A chevron-notch specimen with a size of 2×4×20mm and a chevron-notched precrack of 2mm depth was used. K_{IC} was given by [10] :

$$K_{IC} = \frac{P_C S}{B W^{3/2}} f(C/W) \quad (2)$$

where, P_C is the load at fracture. S is the span length. B , W are the specimen width and height. C is the precrack depth. $f(C/W)$ is a function of C/W , calculated by $2.9(C/W)^{1/2} - 4.6(C/W)^{3/2} + 21.8(C/W)^{5/2} - 37.6(C/W)^{7/2} + 38.7(C/W)^{9/2}$.

0.2% compressive proof strength at 1200°C and 1400°C were measured using an *Instron* model 1195 at a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min. The specimen with a size of 8mm ϕ ×12mm was heated in air, at a rate of 20°C/min and specimen was kept at set temperature for 10min before testing. Vickers hardness at 800°C was measured on 15mm ϕ ×5mm size specimen, using a indentation load of 49N.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructural Features

Typical micrographs of unreinforced MoSi₂, hot pressed SiCp /MoSi₂ and *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ composites are shown in Fig.1. In the polished section of MoSi₂ (Fig.1a), a dark phase was found distributed along the grain boundaries of the light matrix. Its volume fraction, measured by IBAS-2, was approximately 14.2%. X-ray diffraction results indicate that there exist a small amount of Mo₅Si₃ phase in monolithic MoSi₂, which corresponded with the light gray phase (A phase shown in Fig.1a). In hot pressed SiCp/MoSi₂ composite, the phases present include MoSi₂, α -SiC and Mo₅Si₃. SiC particle was easily seen in optical micrograph (the gray phase in Fig.1b). Its size was in the order of 1 to 3 μ m. As a result of addition of SiC particle, change in the grain size of MoSi₂ matrix was observed. In the monolithic MoSi₂ grain were equiaxed and had a size of 9 μ m. In the composite the matrix had a grain size of 3 μ m (Table 1). In the *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ composite microstructure MoSi₂,

Fig.1: Micrographs showing the morphology of MoSi₂ and two SiC reinforced MoSi₂ composites: (a) MoSi₂ (b) hot pressed SiCp /MoSi₂ (c) *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂.

β -SiC and a few Mo₅Si₃ phases were identified by XRD. In the present work composite processed by the *in situ* reaction was better compared to the one processed by hot pressing in term of microstructure and properties. It also had the theoretical density. Small SiC particles (<1 μ m) were dispersed in MoSi₂ (Fig1.c). The glassy phase and cavity were almost absent.

The DTA result showed that there was a large exothermic peak in the temperature range of 1200~1375°C, hence the reaction $\text{Mo}_2\text{C} + 5\text{Si} \rightarrow \text{SiC} + 2\text{MoSi}_2$ could be completed under

Table 1: Microstructural features of three kinds of materials

Materials	Density (gcm^{-3})	Relative density	MoSi ₂ grain size (μm)	SiC size (μm)	Other phases
MoSi ₂	5.72	91.0	9	—	Mo ₅ Si ₃
Hot pressed SiCp/MoSi ₂	5.00	88.8	3	1~3	α -SiC, Mo ₅ Si ₃
<i>in situ</i> SiC/MoSi ₂	5.48	97.5	6	<1	β -SiC, Mo ₅ Si ₃

the present processing condition. In XRD phase analysis, it was found that the major phases were MoSi₂ and β -SiC, consequently the reaction should be completed. Grain size of MoSi₂ matrix observed in polarized light was about 6 μm , smaller than monolithic MoSi₂ prepared by hot pressing.

Mechanical Properties at Room Temperature

The room temperature mechanical properties of MoSi₂ and two kinds of SiC reinforced MoSi₂ composite are given in Table 2. It could be noted that Vickers hardness (Hv) had little

Table 2: Mechanical properties of three kinds of materials

Materials	Hv(GPa)		K_{IC} (MPam ^{1/2}) *		K_{IC} † (MPam ^{1/2})	σ_{FS} (MPa)
	98N	196N	98N	196N		
MoSi ₂	7.88	7.98	2.46	2.01	4.31	414
Hot pressed SiCp/MoSi ₂	10.38	10.59	4.54	4.92	5.95	539
<i>in situ</i> SiC/MoSi ₂	11.05	10.99	3.15	2.57	4.94	534

Note: * — K_{IC} measured by the indentation method

† — K_{IC} measured by the 3-point bend test method

σ_{FS} — Flexural strength

change with increasing indentation load. Hv of unreinforced MoSi₂ was lower than 9GPa, which is that of a single crystal MoSi₂ [1]. This could be due to presence of many cavities in MoSi₂. Pronounced improvement in hardness and flexural strength were obtained by incorporating SiC particle into MoSi₂. This could be attributed to the dispersion strengthening effect of SiC and the fine grain size of the matrix. From the results of the 3-point bend test for the chevron-notched specimens, it was seen that fracture toughness of hot pressed SiCp/MoSi₂ was 5.95MPam^{1/2} (about 38% up) and that of *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ was 4.94 MPam^{1/2} (about 15% up), respectively. In addition, indentation test is a method to measure K_{IC} of a brittle material. The calculation values given by equation(1) were lower than that measured by the bend test. And ones calculated with using two levels of load also had a small

difference (see Table 2). This needs to be studied. Relatively significant improvement in toughness was seen in both the composites. The average indentation K_{IC} of SiCp/MoSi₂ and *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ was increased by 112% and 28% comparing to that of the monolithic MoSi₂. Consequently, SiC particle reinforced MoSi₂ composite not only had an enhanced strength but also had improved fracture toughness.

Fig.2: SEM photographs of the indents and cracks for different materials (indentation load: 98N): (a,b) MoSi₂ (c,d) hot pressed SiCp/MoSi₂ (e,f) *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂

Fig.2 shows the indentation and the cracks along its corner in all the three materials. It is widely known that, in brittle material, the fracture toughness can be enhanced by interrupting the crack propagation through lowering the stress field at an advanced crack tip. For particle or whisker reinforced composite, this may be achieved by the crack deflection, crack bridging or whisker pull-out. In monolithic MoSi₂, an indentation crack traveled primarily in MoSi₂ phase but not in the dark phase (Fig.2b) which indicates that this phase may not be deleterious to fracture toughness of MoSi₂. In hot pressed SiCp/MoSi₂ composite, the crack was likely to pass the SiC particle (Fig.2d) and hence was deflected slightly during propagation. It may be a main mechanism that increased the fracture toughness. In the *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ composite, the indentation crack was shorter (Fig.2e) and passed not only through MoSi₂ but also through the dark reinforced phase (Fig.2f). It was suggested that this reinforced phase had a stronger energy-absorptivity in the process of crack propagation, so K_{IC} of this material was also higher than that of MoSi₂.

Mechanical Properties at Elevated Temperature

MoSi₂ shows a ductile characteristic at a higher temperature, for instance at 1200°C, thereby the sample could not be fractured during bending test (shown in Fig.3). In the case of SiC particle reinforced MoSi₂ composite, the specimen also had a bent shape but the temperature was much higher compared to monolithic MoSi₂, which means composite can maintain its stiffness until a higher temperature than monolithic MoSi₂. It was still

difficult to know the flexural strength of monolithic MoSi_2 and its composite at a temperature higher than 1200°C . In the present work, a compressive test was used to evaluate their high-temperature strength. Above 1200°C , the specimen would be compressed to a drum shape finally as shown in Fig.4, but a compressive yield stress could be read from the stress-strain curve. Fig.5 gives the comparisons of those three materials tested at 1200°C and 1400°C . At 1200°C , hot pressed $\text{SiCp}/\text{MoSi}_2$ had a 37% and *in situ* SiC/MoSi_2 had a 58% increase in strength compared to the monolithic MoSi_2 . At 1400°C , there is an obvious degradation in the strength of all these three materials, i.e, 76% for MoSi_2 , 77% for hot pressed $\text{SiCp}/\text{MoSi}_2$ and 71% for *in situ* SiC/MoSi_2 . But the absolute values show improvement in strength due to SiC particle incorporation. Another evaluation test for MoSi_2 matrix composites was to measure their Vickers hot hardness at 800°C . The result was $6.47\text{GPa}(\text{MoSi}_2)$, $6.76\text{GPa}(\text{SiCp}/\text{MoSi}_2)$ and $7.84\text{GPa}(\text{in situ SiC}/\text{MoSi}_2)$, which also showed the strengthening effect of SiC particle at elevated temperature.

Fig.3: The bending test specimen of MoSi_2 after experiment at 1200°C

Fig.4: Compressive test specimen of $\text{SiCp}/\text{MoSi}_2$ before(left) and after(right) test at 1400°C

Fig.5: Compressive yield strength comparisons at 1200 °C and 1400 °C of three kinds of materials.

CONCLUSION

- 1) SiC particle reinforced MoSi₂ composite was prepared by the hot press process successfully. SiC particle with a size of 1~3μm was dispersed homogeneously in MoSi₂ matrix. SiCp/MoSi₂ composite had a smaller grain size, higher Vickers hardness, fracture toughness and flexural strength than that of the monolithic MoSi₂.
- 2) By utilizing the reaction between Mo₂C and Si powder, an *in situ* grown SiC/MoSi₂ composite was synthesized. It had 97.5% of the theoretical density. SiC had a size smaller than 1μm and was dispersed in matrix homogeneously. The *in situ* SiC/MoSi₂ composite also had improved hardness, fracture toughness and flexural strength.
- 3) MoSi₂ matrix composites prepared by both routes had improved high temperature strength and hot hardness.
- 4) Addition SiC particle into MoSi₂ matrix reflected in improvement in toughness at room temperature and strength at high temperature.

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